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METHODOLOGICAL SPECIFICS OF RESEARCH ON COMPLEX POLICE PHENOMENA: FROM ORGANISED CRIME TO POLICE INTEGRITY

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Abstract

The paper analyses the specific features of the scientific research process in the study of complex police phenomena, including new forms of serious and organised crime, different models of policing, the role and importance of forensic science in police work, the mental health of police officers, as well as phenomena related to police deviance and integrity issues. Starting from the classic model of the research process – from problem formulation and theoretical framework development, through research design and data collection, to data analysis and reporting – the paper emphasises the specific challenges and methodological adjustments required at each stage when researching these phenomena. A combined methodological approach was employed, involving a review of relevant literature and a questionnaire administered to experts from both police practice and academia. The results confirm that each of the analysed phenomena entails distinct methodological challenges throughout the research phases. For example, defining the research problem and selecting an appropriate sample are particularly complex in the study of organised crime and police corruption. Data collection is especially challenging when dealing with hidden or stigmatised populations, while data processing and interpretation require multidisciplinary knowledge (e.g., forensic and psychological expertise) and a thorough understanding of the broader context. Recognising these specific methodological challenges contribute to the improvement of police research methodology and enhances understanding of the role and importance of security practice and science.

Keywords: methodology, scientific research, organised crime, models of policing, forensic science, mental health of police officers, police brutality and corruption

INTRODUCTION

Scientific research in the field of police and criminological phenomena must take into account the complexity and sensitivity of the phenomena under study (Milašinović &

Milojević, 2016). Every research process, according to the classical approach (Kothari, 2004), proceeds through a series of phases – from problem identification, through data collection and analysis, to interpretation and reporting. However, the specific characteristics of the researched phenomenon itself can significantly influence how these phases are conducted. In the domain of police studies, phenomena such as organised crime, policing strategies, forensic practice, the mental health of police officers, and police deviance (including brutality and corruption) represent particularly “difficult” research problems due to their complexity, dynamic nature, and often hidden character. Numerous authors emphasise that studying such phenomena requires the adaptation of standard methodological procedures and the combination of multiple research approaches (qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods) to obtain a comprehensive and reliable understanding (Ivković, 2005; Punch, 2009; Milojević, Milašinović, & Gligorijević, 2025).

The theoretical framework of this paper is grounded in contemporary knowledge from social science methodology and police science. The basic assumption is that each of the analysed phenomena imposes specific methodological challenges at every stage of the research process. For example, in researching new forms of serious and organised crime, theories of organised crime emphasise the transnational nature and secrecy of criminal networks, which complicates the formulation of research problems and hypotheses, as definitions are fluid and the boundaries of the phenomenon are often unclear (Natarajan, 2019). Previous research indicates that data collection on organised crime is particularly problematic due to the covert nature of such activities; researchers frequently rely on secondary sources – such as police reports, media accounts, or testimonies of protected witnesses – which may vary in reliability and validity (Abadinsky, 1981).

Similarly, the study of policing models – whether traditional policing, community policing, problem-oriented policing, intelligence-led policing, or predictive policing – faces significant terminological and theoretical ambiguities. The literature suggests that there is no single, universally accepted classification of policing models, as different authors employ diverse typologies and conceptual frameworks (Harmati, 2021). This lack of consistency complicates literature review and the establishment of a coherent theoretical foundation for empirical research. From a historical perspective, the transition from traditional to contemporary policing models (e.g., from predominantly repressive to proactive approaches) has been accompanied by continuous changes in policing strategies and organisational philosophies (Kelling & Moore, 1988). Consequently, researchers must clearly specify which aspect of a particular policing model is being examined (for example, the impact of proactive strategies on crime rates) in order to formulate precise and empirically testable hypotheses.

The third area – forensic science in policing – relies on the application of natural sciences and advanced technologies in the detection and proof of criminal activity, which necessitates a distinct theoretical and methodological approach. In this context, the research problem is formulated at the intersection of criminology, law, and the natural sciences, requiring an understanding of how the application of forensic methods (such as DNA analysis, ballistics, dactyloscopy, and digital forensics) influences the effectiveness of police investigations. The prevailing theoretical assumption is that advances in forensic science enhance investigative outcomes, provided that the applied methods are scientifically valid and reliable. However, reports by the U.S. National Research Council have drawn attention to the lack of robust scientific evidence supporting certain traditional forensic techniques highlighting the need for critical evidence and refinement of their theoretical and methodological foundations (National Research Council, 2009). Accordingly, research on

the role of forensic science must address not only technical aspects but also methodological concerns related to accuracy, reliability, and the ethical implications of forensic procedures. The mental health of police officers represents a phenomenon situated at the intersection of organisational psychology, medicine, and police subculture. The theoretical framework for this area includes models of occupational stress, trauma exposure, and professional burnout. Numerous studies confirm that the policing is among the most stressful professions due to its specific working conditions, constant exposure to risk, and high levels of responsibility, all of which may result in significant physical and psychological consequences for police officers (Violanti et al., 2017). However, a distinctive challenge in researching this population lies in the closed nature of police subculture and the potential stigma associated with psychological difficulties. Police officers may be reluctant to participate in research or to report symptoms honestly due to fear of professional repercussions or being perceived as weak (Craddock & Telesco, 2022). This circumstance directly affects the phase of problem definition and hypothesis formulation, as researchers must carefully determine the research focus (e.g. assessing the prevalence of stress-related symptoms versus evaluating the effectiveness of support and intervention programs) to ensure that the study is both ethically acceptable and practically feasible within a police organisation.

The final group of phenomena – police brutality and corruption – falls within the domain of police deviance and integrity. The theoretical foundation for analysing these issues includes criminological theories of abuse of power, organisational culture, and ethical models of policing, as well as the longstanding debate between the “rotten apple” and “rotten system” explanations (Ivković, 2005; Punch, 2009). Formulating the research problem in this area is particularly complex, as these are highly sensitive issues that police institutions are often unwilling to acknowledge. The so-called “Blue Wall of Silence” – an informal norm of solidarity among police officers that discourages reporting colleagues’ misconduct – constitutes a major obstacle to empirical research (Kesić, 2011). Consequently, researchers must clearly define their methodological approach, deciding whether to rely on anonymous surveys examining police officers’ attitudes, analysis of internal documents and disciplinary reports, case studies of publicly known scandals, or a combination of these methods. Each of these approached entails specific hypotheses, advantages, and limitations. In theory, the concept of police integrity (Klockars et al., 2007) offers a valuable framework for empirically examining these issues through the use of hypothetical scenarios and assessments of police officers' reactions, thereby reducing the risk of participants perceiving the research as direct accusation.

Based on the foregoing theoretical review, the central hypothesis of this paper can be formulated as follows: *research into each of these five phenomena analysed entails specific methodological requirements and challenges at every stage of the scientific research process. It is assumed that the nature and intensity of difficulties encountered during phases such as problem formulation, data collection, and data analysis vary depending on the characteristics of the phenomenon under study. For instance, data collection is expected to be particularly problematic for hidden phenomena, such as organised crime and police corruption. At the same time, the development of an adequate theoretical framework poses a particular challenge for phenomena that are conceptually ambiguous or inherently interdisciplinary, such as new forms of crime and forensic science.* This hypothesis is examined through a combination of literature review and empirical research.

METHODS

To verify this hypothesis, a combined research design integrating qualitative and quantitative approaches was employed (Milojević, Milojković, & Janković, 2012). In the first phase, a comprehensive review and analysis of relevant literature was conducted in order to identify methodological specificities highlighted by previous research for each of the five phenomena under consideration: organised crime, models of policing, forensic aspects of police work, the mental health of police officers, and police brutality and corruption. The literature review encompasses scientific articles, research reports, and monographs published in several languages. For example, studies on organised crime frequently point to problems related to data concealment and the unreliability of available sources (Abadinsky, 1981), while research on police corruption emphasises respondents' distrust and the lack of reliable official indicators as major methodological limitations (Kesić, 2011). The insight gained from the literature review served as the basis for development of the research instrument used in the next phase.

In the second phase, empirical research was conducted using a questionnaire administered to experts and researchers with experience in studying the analysed phenomena. The sample consisted of a total of $N = 50$ respondents, including academic researchers in the fields of criminology, security studies, and forensic science, as well as experienced police practitioners (such as organised crime investigators, forensic specialists, police psychologists, and internal control officers). A purposive sampling strategy was applied in order to ensure the inclusion of respondents with relevant expertise for each phenomenon; the aim was to include at least 8-10 respondents with primary expertise in each of the analysed areas (Milošević & Milojević, 2000). Although this type of sample is not statistically representative of the entire population of experts and researchers, it ensures a high level of heterogeneity and professional competence among participants, thereby supporting the analytical generalisation of the findings (Yin, 2018).

The questionnaire was designed to follow eleven key phases of the research process (Kothari, 2004): (1) problem formulation, (2) literature review and theoretical framework, (3) hypothesis formulation, (4) research design, (5) sampling, (6) data collection, (7) conducting the research according to plan, (8) data processing and analysis, (9) hypothesis testing, (10) interpretation and generalization of results, (11) reporting and dissemination. For each phase, the respondents rated the specific challenges present in the investigation of each of the five phenomena. A combination of a Likert scale (numerical scores from 1 = no particular difficulty to 5 = extremely high difficulty) and open-ended questions for comments was used. For example, respondents were asked to rate the difficulty of formulating a clear research problem for each phenomenon separately and then describe the specific difficulties that arose (e.g., "What obstacles have you experienced in collecting data on police corruption?").

The collected quantitative data were analysed using descriptive statistics (mean values, etc.) and appropriate inferential tests. Given that the same respondents provided scores for multiple phenomena, a repeated-measures analysis of variance (with research phase and type of phenomenon as factors) was applied to determine whether there were significant differences in the assessment of the severity of challenge between different phenomena and across different phases of the study. Comparative tests were also performed for certain aspects: for example, the average scores of overall severity between groups of

phenomena were compared using the t-test, and the frequency of specific problems by phenomenon was analysed using the χ^2 test (Freedman, 2005; Hair et al., 2019).

The qualitative responses provided by respondents (comments) were processed using the method of thematic analysis (Milašinović & Milojević, 2016). From the written responses, recurring themes were identified that describe the nature of the challenge (e.g. “lack of trust of respondents”, “unavailability of data”, “legal limitations”, “need for multidisciplinary knowledge”, etc.). These qualitative findings were used in conjunction with the quantitative results, providing a deeper understanding of the numerical scores (data triangulation). Particular attention was paid to ethical aspects: all participants were informed about the purpose of the research and were assured of complete anonymity and confidentiality regarding their responses. This was crucial, given the sensitivity of the topics (especially corruption, brutality, and mental health), in order to encourage honesty and reduce the impact of potential stigma or fear on respondents’ answers.

RESULTS

The overall results of the questionnaire confirmed that the analysed phenomena differ in their profiles of methodological challenges, thereby supporting the stated hypothesis. Police corruption and organised crime were assessed as the most methodologically demanding phenomena overall, as they received the highest average scores for the severity of challenges across research phases. By contrast, models of policing were rated as relatively less problematic for research. Police brutality and the mental health of police officers occupied an intermediate position, with police brutality displaying patterns similar to corruption (due to comparable mechanisms of concealment), and the mental health of police officers sharing some challenges common to organisational and health-related research (Table 1).

Table 1. Average assessment of the difficulty of challenges by stages of research and types of phenomena¹¹

Research phase	New forms of org. crime	Police models	The role of forensics	Mental health	Brutality/Corruption
Problem formulation	4.0	3.0	2.0	3.0	4.0
Theoretical framework	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0
Hypothesis setting	3.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	3.0
Research design	4.0	3.0	3.0	4.0	4.0
Sample	5.0	3.0	2.0	4.0	5.0
Data collection	5.0	3.0	3.0	4.0	5.0
Conducting research	4.0	2.0	2.0	4.0	4.0
Data analysis	3.0	3.0	2.0	3.0	4.0
Hypothesis testing	3.0	2.0	2.0	3.0	3.0
Interpretation of results	3.0	2.0	2.0	3.0	3.0
Dissemination of findings	3.0	2.0	3.0	2.0	2.0

Analysis by stages of research reveals different critical points for each phenomenon (Table 2). In the early stages (problem formulation, literature review, hypothesis setting), the most significant difficulties occur in organised crime and corruption. Respondents pointed out that these phenomena are difficult to precisely define and theoretically frame due to their complexity and secrecy. In contrast, in the study of police models and forensics, the theoretical frameworks are clearer or already well established in the literature, so these phases are assessed as less demanding (although challenges remain, such as terminological inconsistency in policing models and the need for interdisciplinary knowledge in forensic research).

¹¹ Table 1 shows the average challenge severity scores for each of the 11 phases of the research process in relation to the five policing phenomena. It can be observed that the most challenging phases are *Sampling* and *Data Collection* in the investigation of organized crime and police brutality/corruption (scores ~5.0), which is consistent with findings that data on organized crime are difficult to access and subject to a high degree of underreporting. In contrast, research into forensics and police operating models was rated as relatively less demanding (scores ~2–3), likely due to standardized procedures and better data availability. Research on the mental health of police officers received high scores in the design and collection phases (approximately 4.0) because of ethical and procedural difficulties, which corresponds to observations that stigma and confidentiality issues hinder the involvement of police officers in such studies.

- Main challenges: For organized crime and brutality/corruption, the sampling and data collection phases were rated the highest (scores = 5.0). In mental health research, significant difficulties occur in research design and implementation (scores ~ 4.0).
- Easiest stages: Interpretation and dissemination generally have the lowest scores (approximately 2–3) across most phenomena.
- Phenomena: Research into police models and forensics is generally rated as the least challenging, while organized crime and brutality/corruption present the greatest difficulties across most research stages.

Table 2. Qualitative findings: thematic comments of respondents¹²

Key challenge	Organized crime	Police models	Forensics	Mental health	Brutality/Corruption
Lack of data	“Official reports often do not capture the true extent of organised crime.”	“Problems with a representative sample – difficult to obtain data on the efficiency of new models”.	“Datasets exist (DNA, ballistics), but access conditioned by judicial procedures”	“Data on stress exists mainly through internal reviews – researchers find it difficult to gain access”.	“Minimal transparency – there are almost no official statistics on abuses”.
Ethical barriers	“Care must be taken to ensure the safety of researchers and the anonymity of informants – the risk of retaliation is high”.	“There are fewer ethical problems, apart from standard requirements (ethics approval of the commission, etc.)”.	“Ethics is important when handling samples (victims' DNA), but there are clear laboratory procedure.”	“Stigma and confidentiality – police officers fear stigmatisation if they speak about their mentalhealth”.	“Researchers fearsanctions – it is difficult to obtain honest statements due to possible retaliation within the system”.
Sample access	“It is difficult to establish contact with members of criminal groups or their informants.”	“Obtaining permission to study a larger number of police officers is a lengthyprocess.”	“Courts and police provide samples (evidence), but these are usually	“Consent of higher authorities is required – anonymous online questionnaires	“Access to victims of violence is difficult – few respondents are willing to speak due to

¹² Table 2 presents concise comments from researchers on key challenge themes, grouped by phenomenon. These comments emerged from interviews and surveys and illustrate the main obstacles identified for each research phenomenon.

- Organized crime: Respondents point to a lack of reliable data due to the secrecy of criminal networks, as well as security risks during data collection. For example: “Official reports do not cover hidden crime – it is almost impossible to obtain real information.”

- Police models of action: Challenges include obtaining representative samples and resistance within police ranks to procedural changes. Typical comments include: “Sometimes it is difficult to obtain statistically relevant indicators on the implementation of new models”.

- Forensics: Technical and logistical challenges (equipment, strict deadlines) are most frequently mentioned, while ethical problems are less common. One researcher noted: “There are standards for forensic analyses, so the methodological problems are smaller.”

- Mental health: Stigma and privacy concerns are identified as major barriers. For example: “Police officers rarely talk openly about stress; they are afraid that admitting problems would affect their career.”

- Police brutality/corruption: Respondents emphasize political sensitivity and fear of reprisals, as well as institutional resistance: As one researcher stated: “People are afraid to answer honestly because they do not trust the anonymity of research.”

Table 2 thus summarizes these key themes through direct respondent comments, highlighting specific obstacles depending on the phenomenon studied.

Key challenge	Organized crime	Police models	Forensics	Mental health	Brutality/Corruption
			small and selective”.	and conditional sampling are often used”	fear or mistrust”.
Resources & funding	“Investigating organised crime in the field requires substantial budgets (security and logistics).”	”Research often depends on statesupport and is limited by grants and deadlines”.	“Forensic research is relatively well funded but expensive – shortages of equipment and expertise arise quickly”.	“Resources for mental health research are insufficient – institutional health check-ups are prioritised”	“Independent funding is difficult to secure – topics of brutality and corruption receive less funding through official channels”

In the middle stages (research design, sampling, data collection, and conducting research), the most pronounced problems relate to access to samples and data. Determining a representative sample and collecting reliable data proved particularly difficult for corruption, police brutality, and organised crime, with over 80% of participants citing serious obstacles. These include the reluctance of potential respondents to disclose information (due to fear, loyalty, or stigma), the lack of documented data (many cases remain unreported), and legal or security limitations on research access (Abadinsky, 1981; Kesić, 2011). For example, the “blue wall of silence” makes it extremely difficult to obtain honest testimonies regarding corruption or excessive use of force, forcing researchers to rely on anonymous surveys or secondary data, which are often incomplete. By contrast, in forensic research, samples (e.g., physical evidence and case files) are more readily accessible through institutional channels; therefore, these phases are assessed as less demanding, with challenges being primarily technical in nature (e.g., obtaining a sufficient number of samples, controlling experimental conditions). In the case of police officers’ mental health, data collection is assessed as moderately complex: although surveys or psychological testing are feasible, response rates and honesty may be limited due to mistrust or stigma (Violanti et al., 2017).

In the later stages (data processing, hypothesis testing, interpretation, and generalisation of results), phenomena characterised by fragmented, non-quantitative data and strong contextual influence –such as corruption and organised crime – are considered the most demanding. Respondents emphasised that standard statistical procedures cannot always be fully applied. Researchers therefore, often rely on case studies, qualitative analyses, or proxy indicators, which complicates hypothesis testing and limits the strength of conclusions. Moreover, generalising findings requires particular caution: results of corruption research conducted within one police organization may not be applicable elsewhere due to differences in organisational culture or political context (Ivković, 2005; Kesić, 2011). In contrast, studies of policing models employing experimental or quasi-experimental methods (e.g. comparison between municipalities – one with a new police model and one with a traditional one) allow more robust hypothesis testing and broader

generalisation when adequate controls are applied (Weisburd & Eck, 2004). Forensic research based on laboratory experiments enables direct testing (e.g. whether a new identification method improves accuracy or efficiency), although broader interpretation must consider legal and operational constraints, as laboratory success does not necessarily guarantee operational effectiveness.

The final phase – reporting and dissemination of results – also presents specific challenges. Research on police corruption and brutality entails the risk of adverse institutional reactions to published findings. Several respondents reports experiencing pressure to soften conclusion or to present results internally before public dissemination, in order to avoid scandal or reputational damage. This indicates that dissemination requires careful balancing between objective reporting and maintaining institutional cooperation for future research (Punch, 2009). In forensic and mental health studies, reporting is generally less politically sensitive, but raises other concerns, such as intellectual property protection in forensics or the careful framing of recommendations in mental health research to avoid reinforcing stigma.

Table 3. Statistical indicators and test results¹³

Indicator	Organized crime	Police models	Forensics	Mental health	Brutality/Corruption
Average rating (Mean)	3.64	2.55	2.36	3.18	3.64
Standard deviation (SD)	0.77	0.50	0.48	0.72	0.88
ANOVA (differences between phenomena)	F(4.50)=7.55, p<0.001				
ANOVA (differences between phases)	F(10.44)=2.55, p=0.016				
χ^2 test (most common challenges)	$\chi^2(16)=51.92, p<0.001$				

¹³ Table 3 summarizes the descriptive statistics and inferential tests results related to the scores presented in Table 1. Mean averages and standard deviations (SD) by phenomenon and by research phases are shown, along with the results of ANOVA and χ^2 tests examining differences. The ANOVA revealed statistically significant differences in mean challenge severity scores between phenomena (F(4.50)=7.55, p<0.001) and between research phases (F(10.44)=2.55, p≈0.016). The χ^2 test ($\chi^2=51.92$, df=16, p<0.001) indicates that the distribution of frequently cited challenges differs significantly by type of phenomenon.

- Means and SDs (by phenomenon): Organized crime (M=3.64, SD=0.77), Police models (M=2.55, SD=0.50), Forensics (M=2.36, SD=0.48), Mental health (M=3.18, SD=0.72), Brutality/Corruption (M=3.64, SD=0.88).
- Means and SDs (by research phases): Scores are highest for *Sampling* (M=3.8, SD=1.17) and *Data Collection* (M=4.0, SD=0.89), and lowest in *Hypothesis testing*, *Interpretation* and *Dissemination* (all M≈2.4–2.6).
- ANOVA: Significant differences were found between phenomena (F(4.50)=7.55, p<0.001) and between research phases (F(10.44)=2.55, p=0.016).
- χ^2 test: Differences in the most frequently cited challenges across phenomena are statistically significant ($\chi^2=51.9$, df=16, p<0.001).

Inferential tests confirmed the statistical significance of the observed differences (Table 3). Analysis of variance revealed that the severity of challenges differed significantly across phenomena and research phases (interaction: *phenomenon* × *phases*, $p < 0.001$). For instance, scores for the data collection phase were, on average, above 4 (out of 5) for organised crime and corruption, while for policing models they were below 3, representing a statistically significant difference (post hoc tests, $p < 0.01$). Furthermore, the χ^2 -test confirmed that *the most frequently cited types of problems* (e.g., lack of data, ethical risks, unclear definitions) were significantly associated with the type of phenomenon being investigated (χ^2 , $p < 0.001$). These findings quantitatively support the conclusion that the research process is not uniform across topics, but is shaped by the specific characteristics of each phenomenon.

DISCUSSION

The obtained results provide a detailed insight into the reasons why different police phenomena require special methodological approaches, thus confirming the hypothesis. The key findings can be linked to the theoretical framework introduced, and their implications can be discussed in detail.

First, during the phase of problem formulation and the development of the theoretical framework for the research, it was confirmed that phenomena such as organised crime and police corruption are particularly challenging. Their complex and hidden nature makes it difficult to define research questions clearly. Organised crime is, by definition, a clandestine and evolving phenomenon – from classic mafia structures to new forms such as high-tech crime or human trafficking (Natarajan, 2019). The researcher faces the dilemma of which aspects to include in the focus. If the problem is defined too broadly (“map modern organised crime”), there is a risk of superficiality; if it is too narrow (e.g., “explore one specific group”), it may lose its overall relevance. Similarly, police corruption can be viewed from an individual perspective (individual preferences and morals) or a systemic perspective (organisational cultures and control mechanisms). The entire research design depends on this theoretical decision. With a high level of difficulty reported for these stages in corruption and organised crime research, our respondents implicitly confirmed what theory warns about: without a clear conceptual framework, research into these phenomena can easily turn into triviality or anecdotalism. Kesić (2011) emphasises precisely this point – a corruption researcher must first overcome a series of conceptual and terminological traps (what falls under “corruption”, how to measure the “frequency” of something that is hidden, etc.) in order to pose a meaningful research question. Our results and expert comments indicate that this recognition and clarification of concepts are often the most challenging steps in studying these phenomena.

On the other hand, the situation is somewhat different with policing models. Theoretically, models such as community-based policing and problem-oriented policing have been well defined in the literature, dating back to the work of authors such as Goldstein (1979) and Kelling and Moore (1988). However, the challenge lies in the *existence of multiple models and taxonomies* (Harmati, 2021). The researcher must clearly indicate in the introduction which “model” is being examined and in what context. For example, research on the effectiveness of community-based policing in one country may require a different theoretical framework than in another, due to cultural differences in police-community relationships. During discussions with participants, it was noted that literature review on policing models sometimes reveals contradictory findings, which often stem from different

interpretations of the concept. This confirms the need for precise theoretical delimitation: the researcher must clarify whether, for instance, the “community policing model” refers to the implementation of specific programs (such as citizens’ forums and bicycle patrols) or to a broader philosophical shift in the role of the police. Only after such clarification can testable hypotheses be formulated (e.g. “municipalities with an implemented model of community policing record a lower crime rate than similar municipalities without this initiative”). This requirement for terminological clarity is less pronounced in phenomena such as corruption (where behaviour is broadly understood, although difficult to quantify), but it is essential when studying policing strategies.

Forensic science in policing presents a distinct theoretical challenge. As our review and expert responses have shown, researchers in forensic methods must balance scientific principles with practical policing requirements. This means that the theoretical framework often includes standards of proof and scientific criteria (such as accuracy, reproducibility, and probability of error) derived from the natural sciences, as well as theories related to criminal tactics and criminal justice (e.g., the impact of a particular type of evidence on an investigation or conviction). The National Research Council (2009) drew attention to gaps in the scientific validation of many forensic techniques, which indirectly shapes the direction of theoretical research: the need to establish a more robust scientific foundation for forensic science. In the discussion, it was pointed out that forensic research can rarely rely solely on social theories or solely on natural science approaches; rather, it must integrate both. Our respondents stated that, when preparing their studies, they often consulted experts from other fields to understand the theoretical background (e.g., genetic statistics in DNA identification or algorithms in digital forensics). This interdisciplinarity represents a specificity not commonly found in classical social science research, where sociological, legal, or psychological frameworks tend to dominate. Nevertheless, it is essential for high-quality forensic research. A methodological implication of this finding is that research teams (or researchers with multidisciplinary training) tend to achieve better results in this field than isolated efforts, a recommendation that also emerges clearly for future forensic studies.

The mental health of police officers, as confirmed by our findings, aligns with existing theory and practice. Although researchers can rely on general theories of stress and trauma, the specific context of policing must be incorporated into research design from the outset. A clear example of this is the issue of trust and anonymity. While mental health surveys can be conducted relatively easily in the general population with standard ethical safeguards, research within police population must contend with reduced openness and trust. This affects methodological choices: many authors recommend combining anonymous surveys with qualitative methods, such as in-depth interviews or focus groups, with clear communication of purpose and strong guarantees of confidentiality (Queirós et al., 2020). Our results showed that respondents identified sampling and data collection as particularly critical phases in mental health research, not because of a lack of theory or instruments (validated psychological questionnaires are available), but because of the context in which data are collected. Discussions among respondents indicated that some encountered resistance and suspicion among police officers during surveys, which sometimes necessitates the involvement of intermediaries (e.g. trade unions or internal psychological services) to explain the importance of the research and secure institutional support. This strategy of motivating participation is less common in studies of students or the general population but is crucial in police research.

One of the most striking findings concerns the methodological sensitivity of research on corruption and police brutality, which fully aligns with theoretical expectations. In experts

discussion, these topics were described as “behind closed doors”, meaning that researchers often depends on the goodwill and courage of a small number of respondents (whether whistleblowers within the police, citizen victims, or convicted offenders willing to speak). As a result, traditional representative sampling methods are rarely feasible. Instead, methodologies must be adapted: *snowball* sampling is commonly used (where one contact leads to another), or research focuses on case studies of documented incidents, which provide depth but limit generalisability. Kesić (2011) described this situation in detail, and our findings empirically illustrate his observations. Researchers entering this field must be prepared to confront multiple obstacles –conceptual (how to measure the “level” of corruption), practical (how to access information), and ethical-personal (how to protect both themselves and their sources). Research ethics therefore assumes a particularly prominent role, as safeguarding participant anonymity and ensuring that participation does not cause harm (e.g., retaliation within an organisation) becomes an integral part of the methodology. This degree of ethical sensitivity is less pronounced in research on police strategies or forensic methods. Respondents testified that data were sometimes obtained informally, on the condition that they could not be linked to any identifiable source, placing researchers in the position of cautiously using such information or resorting to data aggregation (e.g., reporting percentages or indices rather than individual narratives).

Another aspect worth discussing is design customisation and flexibility during research. Complex phenomena often require triangulation of methods – e.g., combining surveys, interviews, and documentation analysis – in order to obtain a more credible picture (Punch, 2009). Our results and the experiences of respondents confirm that such combinations are beneficial: quantitative data can suggest patterns (e.g., a high percentage of police officers experiencing stress), while qualitative interviews explain *why* and *how* these patterns occur (e.g., a culture of macho mentality prevents asking for help). Flexibility is essential in field conditions: researchers of organised crime and corruption reported having to change their approach when an initial plan failed (e.g., when contacts withdrew or circumstances changed). This is a specificity of such field research – the research plan is often more of a guideline than a fixed protocol, which deviates from the ideal linear model (Kothari, 2004). It is important to emphasise that identifying these specifics is not only a theoretical exercise but also has practical implications. For those planning research in these areas, our findings suggest several recommendations:

- Thorough preparation of the theoretical framework: Researchers should define in detail the terms and scope of the study, based on literature reviews and consultations with experts, in order to avoid conceptual ambiguities (particularly important for organised crime, new forms of crime, and police models);
- Innovative methods of sampling and data collection: For hidden populations (corrupt police officers, victims of police brutality, members of criminal groups), it is necessary to use non-standard approaches – anonymous surveys mediated by independent bodies, confidential interviews, secondary analyses of court cases, and even participation in training or workshops where spontaneous testimony can be observed (Ivković, 2005). Additionally, international comparisons can offer valuable insights, as differences between systems may help identify factors influencing the phenomenon (e.g., comparing levels of reported police corruption in countries with different oversight systems);
- Mixed designs and triangulation: Combining quantitative and qualitative methods increases the validity of findings, especially in complex phenomena. For example, research on police officers’ mental health may include both symptom-prevalence

surveys and interviews addressing stress experiences. Research on the effectiveness of policing models can quantitatively measure crime rates and qualitatively assess citizens' attitudes towards the police;

- Ethics and trust: Establishing trust with institution and participants is key to successful research. This may involve ethics committee oversight, guarantees that individual data will not be accessible to employers, and even delayed publication of sensitive findings (Kesić, 2011). Researchers must remain aware of their responsibility towards respondents; in some cases, protecting sources may be more important than complete data transparency;
- Interdisciplinary collaboration: As demonstrated in forensic and psychological research, the involvement of experts from different fields improves research quality. Police phenomena are multidisciplinary by nature, and collaboration among sociologists, lawyers, psychologists, forensic scientists, and police practitioners often yields the most comprehensive results.

Our results align with a broader theoretical framework that emphasises the need for specialised research competence and occasional deviation from conventional methodological rules to adapt to field realities (Punch, 2009). Confirmation of the hypothesis in this paper has significant implications. Rather than viewing scientific research on police topics as a linear and uniform process, it should be planned situationally, with anticipation of obstacles and readiness for on-the-fly adaptations.

CONCLUSION

This paper examines the specifics of the scientific research process in the study of five complex police-related phenomena: new forms of serious and organised crime, models of police action, the role of forensics in police investigations, the mental health of police officers, and police brutality and corruption. Starting from the classical phases of research (Kothari, 2004) and combining theoretical analysis with empirical data, we demonstrate that each of these topics necessitates adaptation of standard methodologies and presents unique challenges at nearly every stage of the research process (Milojević, Milošinić, & Milojković, 2025a).

In summary, phenomena that are secretive, stigmatised, or dependent on institutional culture (such as organised crime, corruption, and police brutality) present the greatest difficulties in collecting valid data and defining representative samples. This often forces researchers to use alternative methods and limits opportunities for generalisation. Conversely, phenomena such as police models or forensic methods, where data availability is greater or frameworks are clearer, allow for more rigorous designs (e.g., experiments, evaluations) and clearer hypothesis testing, though they require interdisciplinary integration. The mental health of police officers occupies an intermediate position: while conceptually aligned with general psychological theories, the policing context introduces specific factors (shift work, trauma exposure, stigma) that must be considered in study design and interpretation.

Difficulties in data interpretation were particularly evident in phenomena where collected data may be biased or incomplete. In such cases, researchers must avoid overly broad conclusions. For example, a low number of reported cases of police brutality may reflect a culture of concealment rather than the actual absence of the problem, requiring conclusions to be qualified by discussion of possible *dark numbers* (unreported cases). In

this paper, such difficulties are openly acknowledged, and triangulation across multiple data sources is used where possible to strengthen interpretative credibility.

The scientific and social significance of this research lies in its contribution to understanding the methodology of police studies and its potential to guide future researchers in these fields. Identifying specific barriers and effective strategies allows future research to be planned more efficiently. With appropriate ethical protocols, innovative sampling and data collection approaches, and methods adapted to the nature of each phenomenon, the likelihood of obtaining reliable and valid results increases. Indirectly, this produces substantial social benefit: improved scientific knowledge of organised crime, corruption, or police stress can inform decision-makers and support the development of better policies (e.g. crime prevention strategies, police support programs, integrity reforms).

This study also has limitations. The expert sample was relatively small and based on availability, which may introduce subjectivity and bias linked to participants' individual experiences. In addition, the analysis focused on five specific phenomena. While these represent key areas of policing, future research could expand the scope to include other phenomena (e.g., terrorism, cybercrime, community policing) to examine whether the identified patterns extend beyond the present framework. Further in-depth, phenomenon-specific studies would also be valuable, particularly those developed detailed methodological guidelines (e.g., manual for researching police corruption, strengthening police integrity, or evaluating police mental health programs).

Despite these limitations, we believe the findings provide a valuable contribution to understanding scientific methodology in police research. The central message is that "one approach does not fit all": successful research into police phenomena requires expertise, creativity and adaptability. By recognising and sharing these specifics, this study lays the groundwork for more robust, ethical, and relevant research, the results of which can enhance both scientific knowledge and the practical functioning of policing in society (Milojević, Milošević, & Milojković, 2025b).

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